

**AN INFINITE FAMILY OF QUARTIC POLYNOMIALS WHOSE
PRODUCTS OF CONSECUTIVE VALUES ARE FINITELY OFTEN
PERFECT SQUARES**

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Abstract

Using an elementary identity, we prove that for infinitely many polynomials $P(x) \in \mathbb{Z}[X]$ of fourth degree, the equation $\prod_{k=1}^n P(k) = y^2$ has finitely many solutions in \mathbb{Z} . We also give an example of a quartic polynomial for which the product of its consecutive values is infinitely often a perfect square.

1. Introduction

Over the last few years, there has been a growing interest in identifying whether certain product sequences contain perfect squares. In 2008 Javier Cilleruelo [1] proved a conjecture of Amdeberhan [2], that the product $(1^2+1)(2^2+1)\cdots(n^2+1)$ is a square only for $n = 3$. Soon after, Jin-Hui Fang [3] achieved to prove that both products $\prod_{k=1}^n (4k^2+1)$ and $\prod_{k=1}^n (2k(k-1)+1)$ are never squares. There are not many similar results for quadratic polynomials. However, in a recent paper [4] two certain cases of quartic polynomials have been investigated in a similar vain. In this paper we will prove, using elementary arguments, that there is actually an infinite list of quartic polynomials $P(x)$ such that the product $\prod_{k=1}^n P(k)$ is a square finitely often. At the end of the paper we discuss some special examples that can be handled by this method. We begin with a polynomial identity which is the key ingredient throughout this article.

Lemma 1. *Let $f(x) = x^2 + ax + b$ be a quadratic polynomial. For every $x \in \mathbb{R}$, the following formula is valid:*

$$f(f(x) + x) = f(x)f(x + 1).$$

Proof. We can verify this just by doing elementary manipulations but we will prove the lemma using a clever observation. Since $f(x)$ is a polynomial of second degree, Taylor's formula gives $f(f(x) + x) = f(x) + \frac{f'(x)f(x)}{1!} + f^2(x)$. This is equal to $f(x)(1 + f'(x) + f(x))$. But $1 + f'(x) + f(x) = 1 + 2x + a + x^2 + ax + b = (x + 1)^2 + a(x + 1) + b = f(x + 1)$. Hence we have: $f(f(x) + x) = f(x)f(x + 1)$. \square

This simple formula will play a key role in the proof of the main theorem. For convenience of notation we set $P(k) = f(f(k) + k) = f(k)f(k + 1)$. It can be seen that $P(k) = k^4 + 2(a + 1)k^3 + ((a + 1)^2 + 2b + a)k^2 + (a + 1)(2b + a)k + b^2 + ab + b$. In the proof of the main theorem, we require a and b to obey a certain restriction. Under this restriction, we are able to prove that equation (1) shown below, has finitely many solutions.

2. Main Results

Theorem. *Let $a, b, m \in \mathbb{Z}$ and $a + b + 1 = m^2$. Then the diophantine equation*

$$\prod_{k=1}^n P(k) = y^2 \tag{1}$$

has finitely many solutions, where $P(k)$ is as above.

Proof. Using Lemma 1 we can rewrite equation (1) as

$$f(1)f(2)f(2)f(3) \cdots f(n)f(n + 1) = y^2$$

which reduces to $f(1)f(n + 1) \prod_{k=2}^n (f(k))^2 = y^2$. Since $f(1) = a + b + 1 = m^2$ we conclude that $f(n + 1) = \frac{y^2}{m^2 \prod_{k=2}^n (f(k))^2}$. It becomes clear that equation (1) is

satisfied whenever $f(n + 1)$ is a perfect square. It remains to prove that among the values of $f(k)$ occur finitely many squares. Write

$$k^2 + ak + b = z^2 \tag{2}$$

for some $z \in \mathbb{Z}$. This means that for sufficiently large k , $k^2 < z^2 < (k + 2a)^2$ if $a > 0$ or, $(k + 2a)^2 < z^2 < k^2$ if $a < 0$. (If $a = 0$ then equation (2) transposes to $(z - k)(z + k) = b$ which clearly has finitely many solutions). Both of the inequalities yield $z = k + c$ for some $c \in \mathbb{Z}$ with $|c| < |2a|$. So, (2) becomes $k^2 + ak + b = (k + c)^2$ which has finitely many solutions as the reader may easily verify. \square

It suffices to choose some nice values for a and b in order to demonstrate the theorem. Choosing $(a, b) = (-1, 1)$ we have $f(k) = k^2 - k + 1$ hence the following:

Corollary. $\prod_{k=1}^n (k^4 + k^2 + 1)$ is a square only for $n = 1$.

Proof. If $(a, b) = (-1, 1)$ then $f(1) = 1^2$. Repeating the previous arguments, it suffices to show that $k^2 - k + 1 = y^2$ has one solution. Indeed, if $k^2 - k + 1 = y^2$ then we must have $k^2 \leq y^2 < (k + 1)^2$ which yields $y = k$ and so $k = 1$. The claim follows. \square

Remark. Arguing as in the previous section, we may present an example which shows that equation (1) has infinitely many solutions. Choosing $(a, b) = (-4, 2)$ we have $f(k) = k^2 - 4k + 2$ and $P(k) = (k(k - 3))^2 - 2$. We can prove that the product

$\prod_{k=4}^n ((k(k - 3))^2 - 2)$ is a square infinitely often. Here we start with $k = 4$ to omit

any trivial case in which the product has negative factors. The product is a square if $f(4)f(n + 1) = 2(n - 1)^2 - 4 = y^2$. It is a routine matter to prove that both y and $n - 1$ must be even. The last equation can be written as $(\frac{y}{2})^2 - 2(\frac{n-1}{2})^2 = -1$ which is a special case of the negative Pell equation $X^2 - 2Y^2 = -1$. This equation has the fundamental solution $(1, 1)$ and all its positive solutions can be found by taking odd powers of $1 + \sqrt{2}$. The positive solutions are (X_n, Y_n) where $X_n + Y_n\sqrt{2} = (1 + \sqrt{2})^{2n-1}$. The next solution is $(X_2, Y_2) = (7, 5)$ which gives $n = 11$. As an

example we can verify that $\prod_{k=4}^{11} ((k(k - 3))^2 - 2) = 246988938224^2$.

References

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